

Issue 1 2025/1

ISSN: 2992-9016

**IS'HOQXON IBRAT NOMIDAGI
NAMANGAN DAVLAT CHET
TILLARI INSTITUTI**

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**ZAMONAVIY FILOLOGIYA MUAMMOLARI
ПРОБЛЕМЫ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ФИЛОЛОГИИ
PROBLEMS OF MODERN PHILOLOGY**

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Administratsiyasi huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligining № 060122
raqamli Guvohnomasi asosida faoliyat yuritadi.
Jurnalda maqolalar o'zbek, rus, ingliz, nemis va fransuz tillarida
nashr etiladi.

www.journal.namsifl.uz

**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB
TA’LIMI VAZIRLIGI HUZURIDAGI IXTISOSLASHTIRILGAN TA’LIM
MUASSASALARI AGENTLIGI**

**IS’HOQXON IBRAT NOMIDAGI NAMANGAN DAVLAT
CHET TILLARI INSTITUTI**

“Zamonaviy filologiya muammolari”, “Проблемы современной филологии”,
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Ushbu jurnal 2023-yildan boshlab chop etila boshlagan. Jurnal yiliga 4 marta nashr etiladi.

Zamonaviy filologiya muammolari - Проблемы современной филологии, Problems of modern philology NamDChTI jurnali O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi (AOKA) tomonidan 2023-yil 25-yanvardagi 060122-sonli guvohnomaga binoan chop etildi. NamDChTI Ilmiy axborotnomasi elektron nashr sifatida NamDChTI ilmiy-texnik kengashining 2025-yil 28-apreldagi kengaytirilgan 2-sonli yig‘ilishida muhokama qilinib, chop etishga ruxsat etilgan (Bayonnoma №2). Maqolalarning ilmiy saviyasi va keltirilgan ma’lumotlar uchun muallif javobgar hisoblanadi.

Namangan davlat chet tillari instituti, 2025 y.

THE DEPICTION OF THE FEMALE IMAGE IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LITERATURE

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ingliz va o‘zbek adabiyotida ayol obrazi tasvirlanishi Abdulla Qodiriyning “O‘tkan kunlar” va Margaret Mitchellning “Shamollarda qolgan hislarim” romanlari orqali tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: “O‘tkan kunlar”, obraz, estetik mahorat, real bo‘yoqlar, “Shamollarda qolgan hislarim”, lirik uslub, satirik talqin, milliy mentalitet, ichki dunyo, ayollik stereotiplari, ramziy ma’no, fidoyilik timsoli, ijtimoiy o‘zgarishlar.

Аннотация: В статье анализируется изображение женщин в английской и узбекской литературе на примере романов «Ушедшие дни» Абдуллы Кадыри и «Мои чувства, ушедшие на ветер» Маргарет Митчелл.

Ключевые слова: «Ушедшие дни», образ, эстетическое мастерство, реалистичные цвета, «Мои чувства, ушедшие на ветер», лирический стиль, сатирическая интерпретация, национальный менталитет, внутренний мир, женские стереотипы, символическое значение, символ бескорыстия, социальные изменения.

Abstract: This article analyzes the depiction of women in English and Uzbek literature through the novels “Days Gone” by Abdulla Qodiriy and “Gone with the Wind” by Margaret Mitchell.

Keywords: “Days Gone”, image, aesthetic skill, realistic colors, “Gone with the Wind”, lyrical style, satirical interpretation, national mentality, inner world, feminine stereotypes, symbolic meaning, symbol of selflessness, social changes.

The creation and interpretation of the female image in literature has an important intercultural significance. The major difference between representation of women in Eastern and Western literature can be deeply contrasted through the analysis of Abdulla Qodiriy’s *O‘tkan kunlar* (*Bygone Days*) and Margaret Mitchell’s *Gone with the Wind*. In literary works, female characters reflect not only the author’s artistic mastery, but also the society’s attitude towards women and the spirit of that historical period. Abdulla Qodiriy, in his first historical novel of the Uzbek national revival literature, realistically portrayed the destiny of women of his time. Meanwhile, Margaret Mitchell, in *Gone with the Wind*, illustrated the emotions and experiences of women during and after the American Civil War.

In Qodiriy’s *O‘tkan kunlar* (*Bygone Days*) (1925), female characters are created within the traditions and values of the Uzbek people and the author’s special aesthetic approach can clearly be seen. The novel presents several women characters

such as Kumush, Zaynab, Khushro‘y, Uzbek Oym, and Aftaboyim. Each of them is described with unique personality traits, and the author uses different artistic and stylistic means to describe them.

Kumush is the main heroine of the novel and she is described as the most ideal image with best character traits by the author himself. In expressing her inner feelings and outer appearance, Qodiriy demonstrates his high artistic skill and creative imagination. The writer conveys her inner emotions through vivid and powerful images, creating a living picture in the reader’s mind. For example, he writes: “...We see a girl lying awake, perhaps reluctant to rise from the cold, or for another reason, in the corner of the room on a silk quilt, in the arms of a feather pillow. Her black hair is scattered untidily on the pillow, her thick curly eyelashes shadowing her deep black eyes fixed on one point, as if she had seen something... Her black, curved eyebrows are drawn together, as if startled by something... Her spotless white face, like the full moon, is slightly blushed, as if she were shy of someone...” Such description of Kumush shows the harmony between her physical beauty and her emotional world. It also reveals the author’s delicate taste in word choice and his lyrical style. From this portrayal, we can understand that Qodiriy treated the image of Kumush with special affection, presenting her as an educated, graceful, intelligent, and courageous woman.

When it comes to the character of Zaynab, she is introduced in the novel as Kumush’s co-wife and as a negative personality. At first, Zaynab appears as an obedient and quiet woman, but as the events develop, the feelings of jealousy and resentment in her heart grow stronger. As a result, she turns into an avenger and poisons Kumush. Unlike Kumush, her fate ends tragically. Through the description of Zaynab, the author shows that jealousy and resentment can completely change a person, filling the heart with the fire of revenge, and in the end, destroying the person herself.

In addition, Uzbek Oym is also one of the female characters that deserves some attention in the novel. As the mother of Otabek, she is mainly portrayed in a satirical way. The author describes Uzbek Oym as an arrogant, aristocratic woman, and reveals these features through her speech and expressions.

In general, in O‘tkan kunlar female characters are represented in different aspects: Kumush — the symbol of pure love and loyalty; Zaynab — the destiny of a woman who falls from jealousy and resentment to revenge; Khushro‘y — the embodiment of intrigue and envy; Uzbek Oym — a character who demonstrates the arrogance and calmness of the national mentality in a satirical form; while Aftaboyim, as a positive secondary female character, is shown as a kind and compassionate mother. Qodiriy, in portraying these diverse women, skillfully uses language tools to reflect their inner world and their role in society.

Margaret Mitchell’s *Gone with the Wind* (1936) is another vivid example of how the female image is represented in English literature. The novel describes the social problems and socio-political life in American society after the Civil War.

Through the images of Scarlett O'Hara, Rhett Butler, Ashley Wilkes, and Melanie Hamilton, the author depicts love and hatred, war and destruction, and social changes.

The main heroine, Scarlett O'Hara, is presented as a strong, proud, stubborn, determined, sometimes ruthless woman who defines her own destiny. According to feminist studies, she is a character who "breaks the traditional stereotypes of femininity." In the novel, Scarlett O'Hara, as a "strong woman" figure, is ready to do anything to protect her family, her property, and her life. Symbolically, she represents the new image of Southern women — the will and strength to replace men during the time of war.

Another female character in the novel is Melanie Hamilton, who is portrayed as loyal, kind, patient, honest, and devoted. She is shown as the symbol of love and selflessness. Although Melanie sometimes seems weak, with her inner strength and morality she wins the hearts of the readers.

Ellen O'Hara, the mother of Scarlett, is described as an aristocratic and strict housewife. She symbolically represents the values that are passed from generation to generation, as well as the role of women in society. Another character, Prissy (an African-American servant girl), is shown as fearful, simple, and sometimes comical. Through this character, the author demonstrates the social position of women in the time of slavery.

In conclusion, the diversity of female characters in Mitchell's novel reflects the different destinies of women in the society of the war period. The analysis of female images in the novels of Eastern and Western writers above shows that in the East the ideal woman is often presented as a victim of devotion, while in the West the ideal woman is represented as someone who achieves happiness through her own effort. For this reason, both Kumush and Scarlett are beloved and influential characters for readers, and through them we can understand different aspects of emotions such as love, loyalty, pride, and perseverance.

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